

On Aggregate Utility Maximization Based Network Management: Challenges and Possible Approaches

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Abstract—F.P. Kelly et. al. have proposed the aggregate utility maximization framework for fair bandwidth sharing among competing elastic demands. This paper advocates extending of the aggregate utility maximization framework for balancing a wide range of the conflicting requirements of the elastic users/contracts. An elastic user/contract is capable of adjusting not only its transmission rate, but also a wide range of burstiness and quality of service parameters as well as willingness to expend resources, such as battery power in a wireless network. The extended framework attempts to maximize the aggregate utility assuming that each elastic user/contract quantifies its preferences with respect to the contract parameters in terms of the individual utility function, and the aggregate utility is a sum of individual utilities of all users. Decentralized maximization of the aggregate utility leads to the minimum cost routing solution, typically with more than one feasible route having minimum cost among all feasible routes. The paper suggests that instability problems of such equal cost multipath routing can be alleviated with Optimized Multi Path Shortest Path First (*OMP-SPF*) routing algorithm. The paper also discusses specific cases of network management solutions, including survivability of the network services and self-organization in a wireless network by resolving trade-offs between user willingness to transmit and depleting the battery power affecting the network life expectancy. Future efforts should be directed towards developing decentralized pricing schemes for complex contracts capable of maximizing the aggregate utility.

Keywords—network management, utility, pricing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional network provisioning models assume that the external demands are fixed and known as a result of statistical projections. Taking external demands as the input these models produce the relevant network provisioning decisions, such as admission, routing, capacity dimensioning, etc., by optimizing the appropriate criterion. Economic models take into account that the network, i.e., service provider, can affect the external demands through pricing. The revenue maximization pricing models attempt to maximize the revenue generated by the network over prices subject to capacity constraints and user price-demand curves. Natural extension of the revenue maximization models allows for the competition among several providers as well as for the capacity expansion/reduction.

In this paper, however, we concerned with using pricing for achieving a “fair” resource allocation in a network of resources shared by elastic users/contracts. Assuming that each user preferences with respect to transmission rates, quality of service, willingness to expend its resources, such as battery power in a wireless network, are characterized by some utility functions, fair resource allocation maximizes the aggregate utility subject to the capacity constraints. The aggregate utility (social welfare) is defined as a sum of individual utilities of all users/contracts. Since unrestricted competition for the network resources may produce “inefficient” resource allocation, pricing may be used to steer the system towards the desired social optimum. Such congestion prices provide signals to the users on the level of the congestion. Elastic users respond to these pricing signals by reducing their demands if the level of congestion increases and vice versa. The congestion prices may or may not relate to real money. In the latter case the response to price signals may be incorporated into the protocol stack and result in modifying the user behavior through appropriate adjustment of the protocol parameters. For example, Explicit Congestion Notification bit (*ECN*) in the Transmission Control Protocol (*TCP*) may be viewed as a pricing signal.

The aggregate utility maximization framework for the elastic users [1] has been proposed by F.P. Kelly, et. al. [2]. This paper advocates using the aggregate utility maximization framework for balancing a wide range of conflicting requirements of the elastic users/contracts, capable of adjusting not only its transmission rate, but also a wide range of burstiness and quality of service parameters as well as willingness to expend resources, such as battery power in a wireless network. The paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly describes the aggregate utility maximization framework for congestion control and routing [2]. Section III suggests that instability problems of equal cost multipath routing, typically arising as a result of aggregate utility maximization, can be alleviated with optimized multipath minimum cost routing. Section IV outlines the aggregate utility maximization framework for resolving various trade-offs among competing requirements, including trade-offs between survivability and economic efficiency as well as between willingness to transmit and life expectancy in ad hoc wireless networks.

II. AGGREGATE UTILITY MAXIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

Subsection A formulates the global aggregate utility maximization problem for congestion control and routing. *Subsection B* describes a decentralized pricing framework for solving this global maximization problem.

A. Aggregate Utility

Consider a network of unidirectional links $l \in L$ having finite capacities c_l shared by users $s \in S$ assuming that users $s \in S$ are uniquely identified by their origin-destination pairs $s = (i, j)$. Let $R_s = R_{ij}$ be the set of feasible routes for a user $s = (i, j)$. User s has utility $u_s(\mu)$ of transmitting at a rate μ , where function $u_s(\mu)$ is strictly concave, increasing and differentiable in $\mu \geq 0$. The purpose of flow control and routing strategies is to maximize the aggregate utility

$$\max_x \sum_{s \in S} u_s \left(\sum_{r \in R_s} x_r \right) \quad (1)$$

over vector of flows $x = (x_r)$ subject to capacity constraints

$$y_l \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{r: l \in r} x_r \leq c_l \quad (2)$$

and non-negativity constraints $x_r \geq 0$.

Sometimes it is preferable to account for capacity constraints (2) by introducing penalty function $f_l(y_l)$ associated with congestion on a link $l \in L$, where $f_l(y_l)$ is a non-negative, strictly increasing and convex function of the aggregate load on a link $l \in L$ [1]. If penalty is "small" for non-congested links and rapidly grows as link load approaches capacity, optimization problem (1)-(2) is equivalent to the following maximization problem

$$\max_x W(x) \quad (3)$$

where the social welfare to be maximized is

$$W(x) = \sum_{s \in S} u_s \left(\sum_{r \in R_s} x_r \right) - \sum_{l \in L} f_l \left(\sum_{r: l \in r} x_r \right) \quad (4)$$

Due to our assumptions optimization problems (1)-(2) and (3)-(4) have unique solution, which can be effectively calculated.

Transmission Control Protocol – Active Queue Management (*TCP-AQM*) may be viewed as a distributed algorithm maximizing aggregate utility in a case when each set R_s is a singleton, i.e., consists of a single route: $R_s = r(s)$. Given a *TCP* algorithm, it is possible to define strictly concave, increasing and differentiable utility function $u_s(\cdot)$, so that the *TCP* equilibrium rates $x = x^*$ solve optimization problem (1)-(2) or (3)-(4). For example, for *TCP*

Reno $u_s(x) = (\sqrt{2}/\tau_s) \tan^{-1}(\tau_s x / \sqrt{2})$, where τ_s is the round trip time for a user s ; for *TCP Vegas* $u_s(x) = \alpha_s \theta_s \log x$, where α_s is the protocol parameter and θ_s is the round trip propagation delay for user s [3]-[4].

B. Distributed Optimization

Solution to the global optimization problem (3)-(4) can be expressed in terms of the congestion sensitive link costs

$$d_l(y) = df_l(y)/dy \quad (5)$$

Define the cost of a route r to be the sum of the costs of links comprising this route:

$$d_r = \sum_{l \in r} d_l, \quad l \in r \quad (6)$$

Given link costs $d = (d_l)$, introduce the minimum cost routes $r \in R_s^*$ for a user $s \in S$:

$$d_*^s \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{r \in R_s^*} d_r = \min_{r \in R_s} d_r \quad (7)$$

It can be shown that the necessary and sufficient conditions for the flow vector $x^* = (x_r^*)$ to solve optimization problem (3)-(4) are as follows: (a) load is carried only on the minimum cost routes and (b) user $s \in S$ transmission rate minimizes the individual net utility:

$$\mu_s^* = \arg \max_{\mu \geq 0} \{u_s(\mu) - d_*^s \mu\} \quad (8)$$

Solution to (8) can be found from eq. $du_s(\mu)/d\mu = d_*^s$.

Optimization problem (3)-(4) can be solved by the following distributed algorithm, proposed in [2]. Suppose that user s chooses a pay rate w_r for transmission on a route $r \in R_s$ and receives in return a bandwidth $x_r = w_r / \lambda_r$ on route r , where λ_r is the charge per unit flow on route r . The user utility maximization problem is

$$\max_{w_r \geq 0} \left\{ u_s \left(\sum_{r \in R_s} (w_r / \lambda_r) \right) - \sum_{r \in R_s} w_r \right\} \quad (9)$$

Consider a situation when user s monitors its rates x_r on routes $r \in R_s$ and instantaneously adjusts parameters w_r by solving optimization problem (9). Under such optimal tracking

$$w_r = x_r \frac{du_s}{dx} \left(\sum_{r' \in R_s} x_{r'} \right) \quad (10)$$

It has been shown in [] that global optimization problem (3)-(4) can be solved by a combination of (10) and the following algorithm for adjusting flows x_r :

$$\dot{x}_r = k \left(w_r - x_r \sum_{l \in r} d_l \left(\sum_{r': l \in r'} x_{r'} \right) \right) \quad (11)$$

III. MINIMUM COST ROUTING

Typically, aggregate utility maximization results in the optimal flow vector $x^* = (x_r^*)$ splitting demands of at least some users among several feasible routes having the same, minimum, among all feasible routes, cost. *Subsection A* discusses instability of Shortest Path First (*SPF*) routing in this situation of equal cost multipath. *Subsection B* suggests that properly designed Optimized Multi Path Shortest Path First (*OMP-SPF*) routing algorithm with a small number of metrics per link may alleviate these instability problems of equal cost *SPF*.

A. Instability of Equal Cost Multi Path Routing

In a situation of equal cost multipath, when the set of optimal routes $r \in R_s^*$ for some user $s \in S$ has more than one element, optimization problem (7) for selecting the optimal route becomes ill conditioned, meaning that solution to this problem becomes very sensitive (discontinuous) with respect to the link costs d_l . From perspective of global optimization problem (3)-(4) a situation of equal cost multipath occurs when optimal routing splits demands of user $s \in S$ among routes $r \in R_s^*$. However, since routes $r \in R_s^*$ have the same costs, minimum cost routing does not have enough information to optimize the corresponding demand split even if technologically such possibility exists. *SPF* implementations usually split load among optimal feasible routes equally [5].

In a case of off-line link weight assignments, this equal split assumption, however, may result in a suboptimal performance. Given minimum cost routing and the equal split in a case of equal cost multipath, maximization of the aggregate utility (4) over the link weights $d = (d_l)$ is NP-hard [6]. A number of heuristics for solving this problem has been proposed [6]. In a case of on-line, adaptive implementation, the minimum cost routing exhibits route flapping instability in a situation of equal cost multipath. This instability is a result of overloading the minimum cost route, so the cost of this route increases and demand is shifted to another feasible route. Then, this cycle repeats. This instability may course undesirable transient effects [7]. In the next subsection we suggest another approach for alleviating these problems: using Optimized Multi-Path Shortest Path First (*OMP-SPF*) routing protocol [5].

B. Optimized Multi Path Shortest Path First (*OMP-SPF*)

Let $d^* = (d_l^*)$ be the vector of link costs (5) calculated at the point of the optimal flow vector $x^* = (x_l^*)$ obtained by solving optimization problem (3)-(4). Consider all possible vectors of link costs $d = (d_l)$ close to this optimal vector $d^* = (d_l^*)$: $\|d - d^*\| \leq \varepsilon$ where $\|\cdot\|$ is some norm. Due to ill-conditioned nature of minimum cost route selection in a case of equal cost multipath, even small variation in the link costs $\|d - d^*\| \leq \varepsilon$ may produce significant variations in the

link loads $x = (x_l)$: $x \in X_\varepsilon(x^*)$. Introduce lower and upper bounds for the link costs resulted from these variations

$$\tilde{d}_l = \bigcap_{\varepsilon > 0} \min_{x \in X_\varepsilon(x^*)} d_l \left(\sum_{r: l \in r} x_r \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\hat{d}_l = \bigcap_{\varepsilon > 0} \max_{x \in X_\varepsilon(x^*)} d_l \left(\sum_{r: l \in r} x_r \right) \quad (13)$$

Now we have two metrics (costs) per link \tilde{d}_l and \hat{d}_l , and the question is how *OMP-SPF* should make routing decisions based on these two metrics.

This question can be easily answered in the following specific case. Let $S^* \subseteq S$ be a subset of all users (origin-destination pairs) for which sets of minimum cost feasible routes R_s^* have at least two elements $S^* = \{s : |R_s^*| \geq 2, s \in S\}$. Consider a case when sets of routes R_s^* do not have any links in common for all $s \in S^*$:

$$R_{s_1}^* \cap R_{s_2}^* = \emptyset, \quad \forall s_1, s_2 \in S^*, \quad s_1 \neq s_2. \quad (14)$$

In this case each link $l \in L$ may be a part of a route from at most one set $R_{s(l)}^*$ where $s(l) \in S^*$. We also assume that each link carries flows from a large number of users, so that the share of the bandwidth allocated to any specific user is small comparatively to the aggregate flow in a link.

It can be shown that in this case the optimal load split $\alpha = (\alpha_r)$ among routes $r \in R_s^*$ for user $s \in S^*$ is given by the following system of $1 + |R_s^*|$ linear algebraic equations

$$\sum_{l \in r} \left[\tilde{d}_l + (\hat{d}_l - \tilde{d}_l) \sum_{r': l \in r'} \alpha_{r'} \right] = \tilde{d}_l \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R_s^*} \alpha_r = 1 \quad (16)$$

In a particular case when all routes $r \in R_s^*$ do not have overlapping links, system (15)-(16) can be solved explicitly:

$$\alpha_r = \frac{\tilde{d}_s - \tilde{d}_r}{\hat{d}_r - \tilde{d}_r} \quad (17)$$

where the ‘‘point estimate’’ for the route cost \tilde{d}_r is the unique solution to the following equation:

$$\sum_{r \in R_s^*} \frac{\tilde{d}_r - \tilde{d}_r}{\hat{d}_r - \tilde{d}_r} = 1 \quad (18)$$

Described *OMP-SPF* routing can be used with off-line calculated or with on-line estimated link metrics \tilde{d}_l and \hat{d}_l . Further research should evaluate performance of these schemes under more general conditions than (14).

IV. RESOLVING TRADE-OFFS AMONG COMPETING CRITERIA

Since typically network performance is characterized by multiple competing criteria, the network management requires resolving of the corresponding trade-offs. Finding the Pareto optimal frontier in space of these criteria and then selecting the desired operating point on this frontier in the distributed environment can be naturally framed as a pricing problem. Once the optimal prices of each criterion with respect to other criteria are identified and communicated to the users, each user can select its contract parameters by maximizing the individual net utility. *Subsection A* discusses resolving trade-off between survivability and competing requirements (see also [8]-[9]). *Subsection B* outlines an approach to self-organization in an ad hoc wireless network resulted from resolving trade-offs between willingness to transmit data and depleting battery power affecting network life expectancy (see also [10]-[11]).

A. Survivability vs. Economic Efficiency

Providing reliable networking services under adverse conditions requires additional resources, e.g., link bandwidth, storage memory, transmission power, etc., as compared to the best effort services. Adverse conditions may be a result of limited reliability of the network elements, such as network links and/or nodes, as well as result of malicious attempts to disrupt the network services by adversary/adversaries. Additional network resources are required to accommodate redundancy needed to counteract the adverse conditions. Conventional research on protection and restoration is usually concentrated on evaluation of various survivability metrics of certain protection and restoration schemes leaving aside the problem of balancing survivability and economic efficiency for each user as well as across various users.

Conventional practical solutions, which offer users a limited set of choices with respect to survivability, attempt to resolve these trade-offs within centralized framework by assigning the corresponding service classes. Price based market framework shifts choices regarding requested services, including survivability levels, to the users, assuming that users are aware of the available services and their prices. The pricing reflects a specific goal of the provider, e.g., social welfare or profit maximization. In this paper we concern with “socially fair” resource allocation intended to maximize the aggregate utility. In the rest of this subsection we illustrate this idea on a very simple, though practical example.

Consider a network where each link $l \in L$ fails with probability α_l and is operational with probability $\beta_l = 1 - \alpha_l$. All link failures are jointly statistically independent. User $s \in S$ utility $u_s(\mu_s, a_s)$ is a function of its data (payload) transmission rate μ_s and probability of successful data delivery a_s . The aggregate utility is

$$W = \sum_{s \in S} u_s(\mu_s, \omega_s) - \sum_{l \in L} f_l \left(\sum_{r: l \in r} x_r \right) \quad (19)$$

where the penalty associated with link loads approaching link capacities is represented by penalty functions $f_l(y)$. Users can combat the adverse conditions by a combination of route diversity and redundant transmissions. Each user $s \in S$ selects vector of rates on feasible routes $X_s = (x_r, r \in R_s)$, so that $\sum x_r \geq \mu_s$. Let the probability of successful data delivery be

$$\omega_s(\mu_s, X_s) = \Pr ob \left\{ \sum_{r \in R_s} x_r \prod_{l \in r} \delta_l \geq \mu_s \right\} \quad (20)$$

where $\delta_l = 1$ if link l is operational and $\delta_l = 0$ otherwise.

Consider the following individual optimization problem for a user $s \in S$. First, given vector $X_s = (x_r, r \in R_s)$, user s selects its data rate μ_s by maximizing the individual utility:

$$U_s(X_s) = \max_{\mu \geq 0} u_s[\mu, a_s(\mu, X_s)] \quad (21)$$

Then, given vector of link bandwidth costs $d = (d_l)$, user s selects its flow vector $X_s = (x_r, r \in R_s)$ by maximizing the individual net utility:

$$\max_{X_s} \left\{ U_s(X_s) - \sum_{r \in R_s} d_r x_r \right\} \quad (22)$$

subject to constraints $x_r \geq 0, r \in R_s$. Under natural assumption optimization problem (22) has unique solution X_s^* , which satisfies the following equations:

$$\partial U_s(X_s) / \partial x_r = d_r, r \in R_s \quad (23)$$

Link costs may be declared by the network or determined by users through probing [2]. This decentralized solution results in the global optimum (3)-(4) if the link costs are “right”. It can be shown that distributed algorithm (10)-(11) can be generalized to find this optimal solution.

B. Self Organization in Ad hoc Networks

Consider a wireless network with a set of nodes $n \in N$ transmitting at rates x_r on routes $r \in R_n$. We assume the following technological and information theoretic constraints on the vector of flows $x = (x_r)$, given transmission powers by nodes $\dot{p} = (\dot{p}_n)$,

$$\varphi(t, X, \dot{p}_s) = 0, \quad (24)$$

$$\psi(t, X, \dot{p}_s) \leq 0, \quad (25)$$

where dependence on time may be due to node mobility.

We assume that if at a moment t node n transmits at rates $X_n = (x_r, r \in R_n)$ while depleting the remaining

battery power p_n at rate \dot{p}_n , this node receives utility $U_n(t, X_n, \dot{p}_n, p_n)$. For simplicity we also assume that

$$U_n(t, X_n, \dot{p}_n, p_n) = u_n(X_n) - h_n(t, \dot{p}_n, p_n) \quad (26)$$

where function $u_n(X_n)$ is an increasing, concave and continuously differentiable function in all arguments $x_r \geq 0, r \in R_n$, and function $h_n(t, \dot{p}_n, p_n)$ is an increasing and convex in $\dot{p}_n \geq 0$, and decreasing and convex in $p_n \geq 0$ for each node $n \in N$. Both function $u_n(X_n)$ and $h_n(t, \dot{p}_n, p_n)$ are continuously differentiable with respect to all their arguments for each $n \in N$.

Assuming that the aggregate utility is additive:

$$U_\Sigma(t, X, \dot{p}, p) = \sum_{n \in N} U_n(t, X_n, \dot{p}_n, p_n), \quad (27)$$

we define the socially optimal trade-off among transmission rates on various routes and battery power expenditure by solution to the following optimization problem:

$$\max_{X, \dot{p}} U_\Sigma(t, X, \dot{p}, p) \quad (28)$$

subject to constraints (24)-(27). This optimization problem yields

$$\dot{p} = F(t, p) \quad (29)$$

$$X = X^{opt}(t, p) \quad (30)$$

Solution (29) forms a closed system of ordinary differential equations with respect to node battery powers $p = (p_n)$. After solving this system, equations (30) determine the transmission rates $X = (X_n)$.

Under natural assumptions optimization problem (3)-(4) is convex and thus can be effectively solved by a centralized algorithm. To obtain a distributed solution consider derivatives

$$\frac{dU_n}{dx_r} = \frac{\partial u_n(X_n)}{\partial x_r} - \sum_{k \in N} \frac{\partial h_k(t, \dot{p}_k, p_k)}{\partial \dot{p}_k} \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial x_r} \quad (31)$$

Since

$$\partial \dot{p}_n / \partial x_r = \sum_{l \in R} \partial \dot{p}_n / \partial y_l \quad (32)$$

derivative (31) can be rewritten as follows:

$$\frac{dU_n}{dx_r} = \frac{\partial u_n(X_n)}{\partial x_r} - d_r(t) \quad (33)$$

where the cost of a route $r \in R_n$ is the sum of the costs of the links comprising the route: $d_r(t) = \sum d_l(t)$, $r \in R_s$, the cost of a link l is

$$d_l(t) = \sum_{k \in N} \frac{\partial h_n(t, \dot{p}_k, p_k)}{\partial \dot{p}_k} \frac{\partial \dot{p}_k}{\partial y_l} \quad (34)$$

and link flows y_l are given by (2).

Once link costs (34) are estimated and flooded throughout the network, each user selects its rates on feasible

routes by maximizing its net utility, e.g., on the willingness to pay basis. Note, however, that estimating and flooding link costs (34) may be expensive in terms of the transmission power and wireless bandwidth. In a case of directed antennas or low rate transmissions evaluation of the link $l = (i, j)$ costs (34) significantly simplifies:

$$d_l \approx \tilde{d}_l \stackrel{def}{=} \frac{\partial h_i(t, \dot{p}_i, p_i)}{\partial \dot{p}_i} \frac{\partial \dot{p}_i}{\partial y_l} \quad (35)$$

Imprecision in link costs poses a difficult question of stability of such cost based scheme. We leave this problem for future research. It can be shown that under quasi-stationary propagation conditions the network settles into quasi-stationary regime with almost constant flow and power expenditure rates.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has advocated the aggregate utility maximization framework for obtaining a wide range of network management solutions for elastic users/contracts. Distributed solutions can be obtained through congestion pricing, where prices either reflect real funds or are simply signals to the users on the level of congestion. In a situation when prices do not reflect real money and user has freedom to modify protocol parameters ensuring that users follow signals provided by prices requires ability of the provider to enforce the desired user behavior. This problem of enforcement can be solved if the network instead of pricing the user behavior prices service contracts, such as parameters of the leaky bucket regulators or parameters of the generalized processor sharing schedulers at the routers.

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